

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF COMPUTERIZED THERMOGRAPHY IN EVALUATING THE EFFICACY OF TREATING INFLAMMATORY BACK PAIN

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Abstract. Medical thermography (thermal imaging): "...a method of recording the natural thermal radiation of the human body in the invisible infrared region of the electromagnetic spectrum of body temperature - one of the most important indicators of human health, based on the fact that any pathological condition locally or generally affects the processes of heat production and heat exchange in the body. Thus, during inflammation, the rate of biochemical processes decreases, but the process of uncoupling respiration and phosphorylation intensifies, as a result of which the temperature of the inflamed area will be higher than the temperature of the surrounding tissues" [1].

Key words: cervical dorsalgia, lumbosacral dorsalgia, quality of life.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ КОМПЬЮТЕРНОЙ ТЕРМОГРАФИИ В ОЦЕНКЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ВОСПАЛИТЕЛЬНЫХ БОЛЕЙ В СПИНЕ

Аннотация. Медицинская термография (тепловизионное изображение): "...метод регистрации естественного теплового излучения человеческого тела в невидимой инфракрасной области электромагнитного спектра температуры тела - один из важнейших показателей здоровья человека, основанный на том факте, что любое патологическое состояние локально или в целом влияет на процессы теплопродукции и теплообмена в организме. Таким образом, во время воспаления скорость биохимических процессов снижается, но усиливается процесс разобщения дыхания и фосфорилирования, в результате чего температура воспаленного участка будет выше, чем температура окружающих тканей" [1].

Ключевые слова: шейная дорсалгия, пояснично-крестцовая дорсалгия, качество жизни.

Thermography normally has a certain thermal body, and in a healthy individual it practically does not change, but pathology changes it. Thermography is absolutely safe for any duration and duration of use; it is used in pregnant women and children, since it has absolutely no radiation exposure - since it registers human electromagnetic radiation, unlike CT and X-ray studies [1, 2, 4, 6]. It is much cheaper than magnetic resonance imaging, it can be used for long-term monitoring of patients, it has a high speed of obtaining and processing information, easy storage and access to research results [5].

Thermography is a non-contact method that works at a distance, which is not unimportant from the point of view of the epidemiology of contact infectious pathologies [14], it allows "... to examine the entire body at once and within the framework of one patient visit, which is also a significant advantage in the thermography method" [5].

The basis of dorsalgia is severe pain caused by irritation of the nerve endings of the soft tissues around the spine: "... muscles, ligaments, fascia; facet joints, nerves and spinal ganglia; intervertebral disc, vertebrae, dura mater" [3].

The causes of back pain are varied. Typically, back pain is associated with pathology of the muscles, nerves, bones, joints or other structures of the spine [7].

Lumbar dorsalgia often occurs at the age of 20-50 years, the maximum pain syndrome occurs at 50-64 years; at 20-64 years old, 24% of men and 32% of women report back pain [8, 9]. The most interesting thing is that 12–26% of children and adolescents also report the presence of lower back pain [11, 12]. Up to 67% of women in the population felt pain in the lower back, and the peak of pain is observed at 35–45 years of age [10, 13].

Purpose of the study: to evaluate the role of computed thermography in assessing the effectiveness of treatment for back pain.

Material and methods. The study is based on examination data of 175 patients with dorsalgia with inflammatory origin of dorsalgia, of which 52 patients with CD and 123 patients with PCD, aged 21-66 years (36.2 ± 6.7 years).

We conducted a comprehensive clinical and neurological examination with active identification of complaints and medical history. Radiological research methods were also used - CT and MRI.

All patients received treatment in a physiotherapy private clinic for a minimum of 10 days.

Depending on the severity of the disease, duration of the disease, contraindications, a complex of treatment was prescribed: massage of the diseased area No. 10; traction of the cervical or lumbar region immediately after massage No. 10; ultrasound therapy No. 5-10 on the diseased area with indomethacin, laser therapy No. 5-10; electrophoresis No. 5-10, UVT 1-2 units No. 3-5.

In addition to shock wave therapy, all physiotherapeutic procedures were carried out regardless of inflammation, at least 4 different procedures per day of treatment.

In the presence of an inflammatory process, anti-inflammatory therapy was performed first:

For mild inflammation (CRP is 1.5-2 times higher): rheumoxicam 7.5 mg 1 tablet x 1 time in the evening after meals for 10 days, on days 3-4 - UVT

For moderate inflammation (CRP higher than 2-3 times, ESR-25-35): xefocam 8.0 mg + Phys. solution 100.0 = IV drip No. 5, (or Ketonal 2.0), then rheumoxicam 15 mg 1 tablet x 1 time in the evening after meals for 10-20 days; mydocalm 1.0 i/m No. 5; after 3-5 days - shockwave therapy, after 10 days of treatment, shockwave therapy was carried out once every 3-5 days, 3-5 times.

For severe inflammation (CRP is higher than 3 times, RF is increased by 2 times, ESR is higher than 35 mm/h): physical solution 100.0 + Dexamethasone 2.0-2.0-1.0-1.0- 0.5 + Analgin 50% -2.0 + No-spa 2.0 = intravenous drip No. 5; xefocam 8mg++Physical solution 100.0=IV drops No. 5 (or Ketonal 2.0), then rheumoxicam 15mg 1 tablet x 1 time in the evening after meals for 10-20 days; L-lysine 5.0-1.0 + Phys. solution 100.0 = IV drip No. 5; mydocalm 1.0 i/m No. 5; after 5 days, shock wave therapy is added; after 10 days of treatment, shock wave therapy was carried out once every 3-5 days, 3-5 times.

Determining the presence or absence of an active inflammatory component of dorsalgia allowed us to make a decision on treatment tactics and its components.

In turn, this group was divided into 3 subgroups using a blind sampling method:

Group 1A - differentiated therapy of dorsalgia of inflammatory origin with subsequent administration of shock wave therapy - 58 patients (16 - CD and 42 - PCD);

Group 1B - differentiated therapy of dorsalgia of inflammatory origin without the inclusion of shock wave therapy - 58 patients (17 - CD and 41 - PKD)

Group 1C – differentiated therapy of dorsalgia of inflammatory origin with subsequent administration of shockwave therapy and vitamin D in therapeutic and prophylactic doses – 59 patients (19 – CD and 40 – PCD);

Statistical data processing was carried out using Microsoft Office Excel-2019, including the use of built-in statistical processing functions.

The results of the study: the dynamics of pain in patients with CD group 1A are leveled out and persist throughout 12 months of observation. So, if initially among patients in this group the average scores were 8.4 ± 1.2 points, then after 14 days of observation they significantly decreased to 5.5 ± 1.2 points ($P < 0.05$), after 3 months to 4.9 ± 1.1 points ($P < 0.01$), and after 12 months to 2.8 ± 0.6 points ($P < 0.001$). The data obtained indicate that the use of shockwave therapy in the complex therapy of CD has a positive effect that lasts up to 12 months.

In group 1B, after 14 days of observation, positive dynamics were noted, there was a significant decrease in average scores on the VAS scale from 7.9 ± 1.1 to 5.5 ± 1.0 points ($P < 0.05$), however, in long-term periods (3 months and year) found an increase in average scores after 1 year to the initial ones, which demonstrates the short-term effectiveness of traditional treatment, the maximum of which occurs in the first 2 weeks and lasts up to 3 months.

In group 1C, a statistically significant reduction in pain was observed relative to groups 1A ($P < 0.05$) and 1B groups ($P < 0.01$), which confirms the long-term effectiveness of the combined use of shockwave therapy and vitamin D, the peak effectiveness of which occurs at 12 months ($P < 0.01$) in relation to group 1A (1.8 ± 0.5 versus 2.8 ± 0.6 points) and to group 1B (1.8 ± 0.5 versus 7.3 ± 1.5 points ($P < 0.001$)).

When analyzing the effectiveness of prescribing shockwave therapy and vitamin D in the complex treatment of patients with PCD, we also noted significant relief of pain. Thus, in group 1A, the initial average scores were 9.2 ± 1.3 points; we noted a significant decrease in VAS scores already on the 14th day of treatment; after 3 months and 12 months, the positive effect persisted, which was confirmed by a persistent decrease in average scores (4.3 ± 0.9 and 3.2 ± 0.5 points, respectively).

In group 1B, regression of the pain symptom was observed during the first 14 days of treatment (8.9 ± 1.4 versus 6.9 ± 1.2 points; $P < 0.01$), while in the long-term period after 3 months and 12 months there was an increase in average points on the VAS scale (7.3 ± 1.6 and 7.8 ± 1.5 points).

In group 1C of patients with PCD, after 14 days of treatment there was an almost 2-fold decrease in average VAS scores (9.1 ± 1.7 versus 4.2 ± 1.3 points; $P < 0.05$), in the long-term period after At 3 and 12 months, pain relief was observed in all patients, with the average scores significantly decreasing compared to the initial data (2.8 ± 0.7 , 1.5 ± 0.4 points versus 9.1 ± 1.7 points; $P < 0.001$). A study of the long-term period showed persistent positive dynamics among patients with PCD when prescribed in combination therapy with UVT and vitamin D.

The degree of muscle disorders in the dynamics of observation among patients with CD and PCD also underwent changes and had a positive trend, so if before treatment the average score on the IMS scale in the groups was on average 12.9 ± 0.18 points for CD, and 9.8 ± 0.32 points, then after treatment there was a decrease in the average score by an average of 3.5 times, a particularly pronounced decrease was observed in groups 1A and 1C (Table 1).

The most pronounced relief of muscular-tonic syndrome was observed in group 1C in patients with CD and PCD, i.e. in patients whose treatment complex was prescribed shockwave therapy and vitamin D. When analyzing the initial indicators of IMS in group 1A, both in CD and PCD corresponded to grade III severity, whereas after treatment it was grade I (mild).

Thus, the average scores on the IMS scale on day 14 in group 1A in patients with CD significantly decreased (12.2 ± 0.12 versus 8.5 ± 0.21 points). In the long-term period, symptom relief in this group reached 3.2 ± 0.11 points. With PCD in group 1A, the average IMS score after 14 days of treatment was 8.5 ± 1.5 points, which is significantly lower than the initial data. After 3 and 12 months, stable relief of muscular-tonic syndrome was observed (5.1 ± 1.3 and 3.9 ± 0.14 compared to 11.6 ± 1.3 points; $P < 0.05$).

In group 1B, in patients with CD, positive dynamics of IMS indicators were noted on day 14; in the long-term period, the average IMS indicators increased and in most patients they reached the initial data or higher. Among patients with PCD in group 1B, a similar picture is observed. The data obtained in group 1B indicate that the relief of muscular-tonic syndrome is unstable and in the long term, in most patients, repeated cases of the disease are observed.

In group 1C, the most pronounced positive dynamics of relief of muscular-tonic syndrome were recorded with a persistent effect maintained in the long-term period compared with the indicators of groups 1A and 1B. Thus, 14 days after treatment, there was an almost 2-fold decrease in average scores ($P < 0.05$) on the IMS, while after 3 months a decrease in average scores was noted by 2.5 times ($P < 0.05$), and after 12 months 4.3 times ($P < 0.01$) relative to the original data. A study of the long-term period showed persistent positive dynamics among patients with PCD when prescribed in combination therapy with UVT and vitamin D.

We also established the leveling of the inflammatory process during thermography. The most typical thermographic manifestation of spinal pain syndrome was the identification of zones with increased intensity of infrared (IR) radiation on the posterior surface of the body (Fig. 1).

Before treatment

After treatment

Rice. 1. Pathological hyperthermia of the posterior surface of the neck in CD. Thermogram (a) and pseudo-three-dimensional image (b) of the posterior surface of the neck

Depending on the localization and severity of the pathological process, various variants of disruption of normal thermotography of the posterior surface of the body were diagnosed: thermal asymmetry of the thermal pattern, zones of increased emission of infrared radiation in the area of the skin projection of the spinous processes of the vertebrae (individually several or throughout the entire spinal column), foci of confluent and spotted pathological hyperthermia in paravertebral zones.

Having analyzed the changes in thermal imaging data before and after treatment, we can say that after treatment, the values of absolute temperature in the neck area change unreliably in the treatment groups.

However, in groups 1A and 1C in the neck region there was a decrease in maximum temperature - on average by $1.8 \pm 0.01^\circ\text{C}$ and $2.3 \pm 0.01^\circ\text{C}$ ($35.4 \pm 1.2^\circ\text{C}$ and $35.8 \pm 1.1^\circ\text{C}$ before treatment and $33.6 \pm 1.3^\circ\text{C}$ and $33.5 \pm 1.2^\circ\text{C}$ after treatment, respectively) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Thermometry indicators for CD in treatment groups during follow-up

In group 1B, temperature indicators before and after treatment changed by $0.8 \pm 0.01^\circ\text{C}$, which is significantly lower in relation to groups 1A and 1C ($P < 0.01$).

When studying thermographic indicators in the dynamics of treatment in patients with PCD, we established the following temperature changes, so in patients of groups 1A and 1C we

found a statistically significant decrease in thermal asymmetry in all studied regions ($p < 0.05$). In the PCD region, the most pronounced decrease in thermal asymmetry was observed after treatment ($p < 0.05$).

Before treatment, the study groups did not differ in thermal asymmetry ($p > 0.05$). In group 1B there was also a change in thermal asymmetry after treatment, but not as strong as in groups 1A and 1C (Fig. 3).

Fig.3. Thermometry indicators for CD in treatment groups during observation dynamics

As can be seen from the diagram, in patients of group 1A, a decrease in temperature was found on average by $2.2 \pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$, while in group 1B it was only by an average of $0.8 \pm 0.01^\circ\text{C}$, which is significantly lower ($P < 0.05$). However, in group 1C, the average deviations in the dynamics of the study were $3.2 \pm 0.06^\circ\text{C}$, which was significantly higher in relation to groups 1A and 1B ($P < 0.01$) (Fig. 4).

Based on the results obtained, it can be argued that in case of dorsalgia, an informative indicator of the level of pain is the severity of thermal asymmetry in the neck and lumbosacral region. The criterion for improving the condition of patients can be not only a decrease in maximum temperature, but also a decrease in thermal asymmetry.

Fig.4. Pathological hyperthermia of the spine during PCD. Thermogram (a) and (b) after treatment; (c) before treatment

Based on this, we can talk about a decrease in inflammatory processes, irritation phenomena and venous stagnation in patients who received shockwave therapy and vitamin D.

Conclusion: thermographic monitoring of such patients during the process of rehabilitation treatment showed that in most cases, subjective normalization occurs earlier than the ICTG indicators return to normal. This makes it possible to very reliably diagnose residual effects of the inflammatory process and, if necessary, continue rehabilitation measures.

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